

DESCRIPTION OF THE LINAC CONTROL ROOM

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Abstract

At the request of the exhibitions service, this is a short description of the equipment used to control CERN's second linear accelerator, Linac II, which distributed protons to the complex from 1978 through 2018.

INTRODUCTION

In 1976, while CERN's second linear accelerator, Linac II, was being built, its control room was already operational. It was inspired by the design of the SPS' control room [1], which paved the way for the appearance and workings of control rooms over the last quarter of the 20th century, much like the CCC for the following one [2].

The figures illustrating this document are photographs which have been taken during the development phase of the controls for the "new" Linac [3], due to start two years later [4].

These pictures will be used to explain the workings of the control system to visitors, as a new itinerary is being designed throughout the South Hall.

THE CONTROL SYSTEM

The computers

The Linac II control system [5] was based on a pair of DEC PDP11 mini-computers, the "Main Computer" (MAC) and the "Front End Computer" (FEC), running the DEC RSX11 operating system, and communicating over a DR-11B link (Fig. 1). This arrangement would nowadays be called a "local area network". The FEC was used to access the equipment in real-time. The MAC, operating asynchronously, dealt with the user interface, sending requests to the FEC, controlling the equipment and returning acquired measurements to the operation crews [6].

Figure 1: Racks housing the FEC (on the left) and MAC (on the right) PDP-11 mini-computers.

The control system interfaced with the accelerator hardware through a digital CAMAC loop accessing analogue NIM modules (Fig 2. & 3).

Figure 2: A. Van Der Schueren next to the racks housing digital CAMAC and analogue NIM modules.

Figure 3: Racks housing analogue NIM modules.

In addition, an off-line PDP-11 computer, also equipped with its own CAMAC loop and simulation equipment, was used as a development machine, to write and tests programs before releasing them onto the actual control system (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Development system.

The consoles

The human interface was lodged into a metallic body, deep enough to house the cathode ray screens, specific electronics, and their ventilation systems. The main console (Fig. 5) was organised as a quarter of a circle. It comprised four workstations, each consisting in (Fig. 6):

- A colour screen displaying 25 lines 40 characters
- An oscilloscope
- A touch screen, with 16 sensitive rectangular areas
- A numeric keypad with its LED mini display
- Four shaft encoders
- Four pairs of incremental/decremental buttons

In the middle of the main console, were also a telephone, three intercom stations with hardwired links to various parts of the complex, two computer terminals, two special high resolution graphic screens, and additional oscilloscopes.

Figure 5: General view of the main console.

Figure 6: Detail of a workstation: colour screen, oscilloscope, touch screen, numeric keypad and LED display, shaft encoders and incremental buttons.

The colour screen was able to display alphanumeric as well as graphics characters. This allowed, already at the time, to produce relatively sophisticated plots of beam parameters (Fig. 7).

A generic “synoptic” program (Fig. 8) was also written to show and control specific parts or systems of the machine.

Finally, an extra workstation was installed in a mobile console (Fig. 9). This mobile console was not intended to stay in the control room, but to travel close to the power supplies or radio frequency amplifiers, in order to control them locally, mainly during commissioning or debugging phases.

Figure 7: Test of multiple graphics on the colour screen.

Figure 9: Mobile console.

Figure 8: Test of a synoptic display, with dummy equipment names.

Interaction with the equipment

The simplest way of interacting with the machine was to display up to four individual control parameters (current in a magnet, phase or voltage of an RF tank, ...) on the colour screen. The selection process was done through a tree-like menu on the touch screen. Once selected, the current control value (CCV) was displayed, as well as the acquisition value measured. It was then possible to modify the CCV by entering an absolute number on the keypad, to increment or decrement it using the buttons, or to fine tune it with the shaft encoders.

Some areas of the machine could be displayed using a synoptic program, allowing the user to monitor a large set of parameters.

A few application programs were written for specific needs, such as global trajectory corrections.

Finally, any relevant analogue signal pertaining to the accelerator could be displayed on a trace of one of the oscilloscopes. As for the control of individual parameters, the selection process was done through a tree-like menu on a touch screen.

CONCLUSION

Hoping this short document has shed some light on the inner workings of the New (at the time) Linac Control Room, the author stays at the disposal of the exhibitions service for more detailed explanations.

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